

THE USE OF ALTERNATIVE MATERIALS IN A LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

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Abstract: *The article is dedicated to the study of various researchers' viewpoints on the importance of using authentic materials and explores the ways in which they are selected for a class.*

Key words: *homegrown materials, comprehensible and attractive, target language, real situations, communicative approaches, trialing, authenticity.*

Alternative teaching material can be any material used in the English classroom excluding coursebooks. Usually the concept of coursebook includes not only textbook and workbook but also recordings and other material offered in a package from a publisher (Woodward 2001: 145). Coursebooks can also be placed in a category called ready-made material. Alternative material is mainly referred to as 'authentic' or 'real-life material'. Mitchell (1995:39) describes authentic material as material that was originally produced for native speakers. According to this criterion authentic teaching material can for example consist of magazines, newspapers or recordings of real-life conversations. Little et al (ibid 1995:45) define authentic texts as follows:

An authentic text is a text that was created to fulfil some social purpose in the language community in which it was produced. Thus novels, poems, newspaper and magazine articles, handbooks and manuals, recipes and telephone directories are all examples of authentic texts; and so too are radio and television broadcasts and computer programmes.

Obviously, there is a wide range of texts to choose from when searching for alternative teaching material. In Kramsch's (2000:177) view "the term 'authentic' has been used as a reaction against the prefabricated artificial language of textbooks and instructional dialogues; it refers to the way language is used in non-pedagogic, natural communication". Moreover, Harmer (2001: 151) contributes with an additional term for alternative teaching material: 'homegrown materials'. Primarily this is material made by teachers themselves, for example overhead

transparencies, pictures, worksheets with exercises (grammar, vocabulary etc). This 'homemade' material is often designed with the help of authentic texts such as articles from newspapers or magazines, books or the Internet. Furthermore, there is even an expression for teachers who prefer to create their own material to using coursebooks: "do-it-yourself" teachers, who of course have their own "do-it-yourself" approach (ibid 2001: 304f). In conclusion, alternative teaching material is authentic, often self-made by teachers, originally created for native speakers and mainly does not include the kind of artificial language that often occurs in coursebooks.

The production of alternative material

Harmer (2001:151) suggests a five-stage procedure when teachers make their own teaching material. Focus is put on the making of the material rather than the actual use of it. The first stage is planning and to begin with all the material obviously needs to be comprehensible and attractive to the students. In order for the material to achieve these criteria one can have Krashen's Input Hypothesis (in Brown 2000:278) in mind when deciding how challenging the material should be for the students. This hypothesis argues that:

[an] important condition for language acquisition to occur is that the acquirer understand (via hearing or reading) input language that contains structure 'a bit beyond' his or her current level of competence... If an acquirer is at stage or level i , the input he or she understands should contain $i + 1$.

It is therefore important for the teacher who creates the material that he or she makes sure to present a language that the students can understand and that simultaneously challenges the students to make progress (ibid). Furthermore, topics must be chosen and also what activities are required from the students (reading, speaking, writing, etc). Aims ought to be considered as well and are very important. Trialling is the next stage and refers to trying out the material before it is used in the classroom. In order to do this, colleagues, a friend or a student can be asked for their opinions about the newly produced material. In this way spelling mistakes or vague instructions can be discovered in time. The third stage is evaluating which contributes to improving the material for future use and also provides ideas about the production of other materials. The following stage is classifying, (e.g. to categorize the material alphabetically) a useful process in order to access the material easily for future use. There could be as many ways of classifying as there are teachers. Lastly, there is record-keeping which reminds of classifying. It is very useful for long-term planning to have documentation of

material and evaluations, especially if it is to be used in different classes (Harmer 2001:151).

The communicative approach and the importance of authenticity

According to Kramsch (2000:185) communicative approaches to language teaching emphasize exposing second language learners to spoken or written texts that are authentic, that is to say containing no artificial language that is produced for pedagogic purposes. The intention of authentic communication is to make learners better understand both “speaking customs and 4 ways of life of the target country” in order to behave more native-like. This approach is especially useful for teaching immigrants in English-speaking countries (ibid).

Mitchell (1995:39) also emphasizes the importance of authenticity in the communicative approach and claims that it is a ‘key concern’ for this approach. Authentic material help language learners to appreciate it as a link to the real world outside the English classroom. This accustoms learners to becoming familiar with the target language and prepares them for real situations. Lightbown and Spada (1999:168) too observe students’ need to deal with authentic material so they can prepare themselves for language situations outside the classroom.

Tornberg (2000:17) further points to the significance of meaningful and authentic teaching material and observes a problem in schools where students are expected to acquire knowledge that has been established outside the classroom. This knowledge is then supposed to be mediated in a way that makes students capable of seeing a connection between the classroom and the real world. If this connection is absent and school reality consists of a worn down classroom and coursebooks that are out of date, there exists a risk that pupils only associate language with what happens in the English classroom and what is tested in exams. Their language acquisition then ends up in a ‘no-man’s-land’ where there is a great distance to native-speakers and their world (ibid). Nevertheless, if authentic material is used, this distance can be reduced.

However, Mitchell (1995:40) points out that there is a problem with the communicative approach: the question of grammar. When students are encouraged to speak as much as possible and focus is on meaning rather than on form, they often make grammatical mistakes. Many teachers solve this problem by teaching grammar in traditional ways and simultaneously use authentic material as their main resource. Mitchell (ibid) quotes Brumfit who points out that “teachers should plan systematically for a balance between meaning-oriented ‘fluency’ work and form-oriented ‘accuracy’ work”.

Kramersch (2000:178) claims that there has been an increased need to develop both communicative and cultural competence in language teaching. In order to fill these needs the use of authentic texts becomes salient. However, to merely use authentic texts is not enough to make it authentic according to Kramersch. The ultimate situation is to use a text as it was intended to be used originally. If for example a German menu is utilized for grammatical practise, it is not used in the way native customers make use of it at a restaurant (ibid). However, whether this is relevant or not when using authentic texts in the English classroom, could be discussed.

Moreover, in the same way as in natural situations we read texts for different purposes, the choice of text and reading practise should also result in students learning how to deal with different sorts of text in a realistic way, preferably taken directly as authentic texts from newspapers or magazines. Every text does not have to be used for learning grammar or extending one's vocabulary. Sometimes it is sufficient merely to read a text and understand its main points (Tornberg 2000:79).

Coursebooks versus alternative material. Many teachers choose to use coursebooks as their main resource in the classroom whereas some teachers use them only to complement alternative material. Lundahl (1998:11) believes that there is a reason to react if an entire course revolves around coursebooks and suggests a combination of coursebooks and alternative material. Furthermore, he remarks that there are many advantages with authentic texts; "above all they give students a chance of meeting contents that interest them, stories that fascinate and linguistic challenges that cannot be offered by coursebooks" (ibid, my translation). However, he also points out that several coursebooks today provide texts of good quality. What are the advantages and disadvantages of using coursebooks and alternative material respectively? Unfortunately there is not enough time and space for mentioning all possible aspects in this study and therefore only some will be brought up.

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